

Developing practical support for Women in Crop Science

Report from CIMMYT Women in Crop Science meeting – May 2022

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Summary

The role and contribution of women in crop science is significant. Recent events and engagements have aimed to highlight and build greater support within the community (including but not limited to Dixon *et al.* (2022) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6511355>). This includes the recently developed Women in Crop Science Directory (to join, complete this short form: <https://tinyurl.com/yhdefpmj>) which will provide meeting organizers and other stakeholders with contact information of women working across the broad spectrum of crop sciences globally.

CIMMYT Women in Crop Science meeting

During a recent meeting held on 18th May, 2022 in Nairobi, Kenya, we started a dialogue with a group of female scientists working at the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT) about practical support for women in crop science. This covered two questions: (1) What do you want in a mentor?; (2) What career development opportunities do you want to see?

A summary of the responses is given below.

1. What do you want in a mentor?

Mentoring is an effective method to build confidence and to support professional development of individuals. Many business commentators report it as an important strategy to close the gender gap, particularly in leadership (e.g. <https://womenintheworkplace.com/>). However, the parameters and requirements of mentoring women in the crop science community are not well understood. Participants agreed that mentors should provide honest, constructive, and critical feedback as well as a safe space to engage, communicate and share goals. Participants in the meeting felt that it is important to clearly define the difference (and differing expectations) between the role of a supervisor and the role of a coach or mentor.

It is also key to specify the value that a mentor brings. This includes their ability to provide guidance on how to achieve work-life balance and how to navigate pathways and steps for career progression. Open and honest dialogue on mentee strengths and weaknesses in the context of their current situation is vital. The context of a mentee's current work and life situation is crucially important in selection of a mentor. This ensures a relationship that can provide relevant support, rather than providing guidance based on vastly different work and life situations in the past. Opportunities for peer-to-peer mentoring should be fostered within the community given the current imbalance between men and women in leadership

positions. Training for mentors is needed as well to understand expectations of their mentorship.

2. What career development opportunities do you want to see?

The group discussed a wide variety of career development opportunities. There is a need for targeted, rather than generic training offered by organizations. Participants welcomed the opportunity to create a forum to share trainings, learnings, and work experiences. One example would be the opportunity to create a regional discipline-based exchange program to expose women to other organizations and ways of working whilst retaining their current positions. Unconscious bias training for all employees in an organization was seen as essential to make faster progress against existing biases. Time dedicated to undertaking courses and training for career development should be recognized, acknowledged, and rewarded rather than being an expectation on top of work tasks.

Female scientists should be supported when attending scientific and community events, particularly when attending for the first time. The participants, who represented a range of career stages at CIMMYT, also welcomed a forum for more junior female (and male) staff (e.g. research associates and interns) to present at internal, external and partner meetings. A final recommendation was to further build an internal and external Women in Crop Science cohort and to offer soft skills and other training activities through this group. This recommendation will be taken forward with the Women in Crop Science Directory in the form of quarterly soft skills and career development webinars.